

Citation for the Presentation of the
2010 ICPE Medal to

Professor Gunnar Tibell

Professor Emeritus at University of Uppsala,
Sweden

The Commission is pleased to announce the award of the ICPE Medal for the year 2010 to Gunnar Tibell, Professor Emeritus at University of Uppsala, Sweden. An experimental nuclear physicist, he is well known for his contributions as the Chairman of the Swedish Physical Society 1989-95, and the European Physical Society, where he played an influential role with his strong advocacy for the cause of physics education at all levels. As Chair of the EPS Physics Forum and later within the Physics Education Division, he vigorously supported a wide range of educational activities, including pre-university education, student mobility programmes, international exchanges for physics teachers and student competitions.

He is especially known for spearheading the International Young Physicists Tournament for ten years as President from 1999. See: (<http://www.iypt.org/new/>) Prof. Tibell served as a member of ICPE from 1999 to 2002 and was Chair from 2002 to 2005. His deep engagement with EPS and other international physics organizations led to greater synergy that strengthened global exchanges for development of physics education programmes.

Established in 1979 on suggestion from George Marx, the ICPE medal recognises outstanding contributions to physics education that transcend national boundaries; are major in scope and impact; and have extended over a considerable period of time.

Prof. Tibell received the medal at a ceremony organized at the ICPE's conference in Mexico in August 2011.